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THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN LEARNING AND TEACHING A SECOND LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Recent years have seen a massive increase in English language teaching and learning as well, the reason for this is English language has become the lingua franca through all of the world. As a result of this, English teaching has begun to be increasingly vital. Unlike the previous century, it is more crucial to teach communication than grammar-translation nowadays, which is being applied by many instructors in modern area. Yet, there are some challenges for learners to communicate effectively. This case entails small-scale research on listening comprehension, reasons for misunderstandings, and inappropriate responses in real situations and provides some possible solutions.

Key words: Communicative competence, audio-lingualism, transformational grammar, traditional methods, grammar-translation method.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ И ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ВТОРОГО ЯЗЫКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В последние годы наблюдается значительный рост преподавания и изучения английского языка, причина этого в том, что английский язык стал лингва-франка во всем мире. В результате этого преподавание английского языка стало приобретать все большее значение. В отличие от прошлого века, в настоящее время более важно учить общению, чем грамматике-переводу, который применяется многими преподавателями в современных областях. Тем не менее, есть некоторые проблемы, с которыми учащиеся сталкиваются при эффективном общении. Этот случай включает в себя небольшое исследование понимания на слух, причин непонимания и неуместных ответов в реальных ситуациях и предлагает некоторые возможные решения.

Ключевые слова: Коммуникативная компетенция, аудио-лингвистика, трансформационная грамматика, традиционные методы, грамматико-переводной метод.

IKKINCHI TILNI O'RGANISH VA O'QITISHDA KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTSIYANING AHAMIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

So'nggi yillarda ingliz tilini o'qitish va o'rganishda katta o'sish kuzatildi, buning sababi ingliz tili butun dunyo bo'ylab lingua francaga aylandi. Buning natijasida ingliz tilini o'rgatish tobora muhim

ahamiyat kasb eta boshladi. O'tgan asrdan farqli o'laroq, zamonaviy sohada ko'plab o'qituvchilar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan grammatik tarjimadan ko'ra muloqotni o'rgatish muhimroqdir. Biroq, o'quvchilarning samarali muloqot qilishlari uchun ba'zi qiyinchiliklar mavjud. Bu holat tinglab tushunish, tushunmovchiliklar sabablari va real vaziyatlarda nomaqbul javoblar bo'yicha kichik miqyosli tadqiqotlarni o'z ichiga oladi va ba'zi mumkin bo'lgan yechimlarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kommunikativ kompetentsiya, audio-lingualizm, ransformatsion grammatika, an'anaviy usullar, grammatika-tarjima usul.

1. Introduction.

English is often called "the lingua franca of the whole world". Recent years have seen a massive increase in English language teaching worldwide, not only in schools but also in factories and elsewhere. The knowledge of English is required by many employers and in many other parts of people's life. It will be essential to understand English very well in the future, and this is the reason for finding better and more enjoyable ways to start teaching learners. As a result of this, English teaching has begun to be increasingly vital. Unlike the previous century, it is more crucial to teach communication than grammar-translation nowadays, which is being applied by many instructors. English grammar had always been an initial purpose to learn for students as it was highly required by many institutes and universities in my country. Fortunately, starting with the previous year, international certificates have been accepted, and now mentors, as well as learners, are trying to find out effective ways of becoming competent in learning foreign languages. Yet, there are some challenges for learners to communicate effectively. This case entails small-scale research on listening comprehension, reasons for misunderstandings, and inappropriate responses in real situations and provides some possible solutions. There are several demands to learn about audio communicative competence theory. The research of any language demands to learn its structure and to be able to use it in all effective as well as correlative manners: through speaking, reading, writing, and listening as well. All these skills encompass informing and receiving thoughts and ideas through communicating. Being able to communicate fluently and effectively has to contain the process of intellectual gaining techniques that could be clarified to the listener involved. Communicative competence demands to be able to comprehend ideas, implying these things properly as well as convincingly requirements of knowledge of the cultural characteristics of the listeners. The study of a commonly spoken language, at any kind of degree, has to help students to apply it spontaneously and appropriately in familiar and in unfamiliar situations. Nowadays, in Uzbekistan, English language courses mainly focus on different interactive and communicative as much as possible, characterizing various requirements of language proficiency.

II. Literature Review

In the past a language was considered to be a set of grammatical structures as phonemes, morphemes, and syntax. All these aspects of linguistics could be learned through drilling grammar as well as pronunciation. S. J. Savignon (2002) claims that with continued government support for materials development and teacher training, audio-lingual method somehow promoted language teaching to a science. It became quite popular across many countries to apply all four skills: listening, reading, speaking and writing through learning by heart ready dialogs, which assisted students to prevent mistakes, but I think it was unnatural. Including several reasons and the invention of tape recorder language learners in non-English speaking countries had a chance to listen to native-speaker models of pronunciation and grammar and improve their listening skill.

One of the first theories about audio-lingualism was introduced by Noam Chomsky (1959), an influential American educator and a structural linguist, a philosopher, cognitive scientist and a political activist, often called one of the fathers of modern linguistics that human language development (linguistic competence) was much more creative than that represented by Skinnerian behaviorisms. Chomskian revolution resulted in the establishment of independent departments of linguistics at major universities. Besides, his theory of transformational grammar is a very important and revolutionary theory in the linguistics. After a certain period of time, a sociologist called Dell Hymes (1972) used the term communicative competence in order to provide a much broader view of

the language and he added different elements to those discussed by Chomsky and was influenced by the Prague School of functional linguistics. It is undeniable that speakers need to know not only grammatical structures but norms of appropriate usage in a context. Subsequently, Swain (1980) amended the earlier notion of strategies that as may be called into action either to enhance the effectiveness of communication or compensate for breakdowns well as Bachman (1990) developed models building on Hymes's work for L2 teaching and testing.

Communication might be regarded as a combination of acts, a series of elements with purpose and intent. Communication is not merely an event, something that happens, it is rather functional and purposive and predicted to bring some effects, suitable changes, subtle or unobservable on the environment of hearers and speakers. Communication is a series of communicative acts or speech acts, which are used systematically to reach some aims. John Austin (1962) pointed out the importance of consequences, the perlocutionary force, of linguistic communication. After that, many researchers have been trying to examine communication in terms of the outcome that spoken speech achievements. Second language learners have to realize the aim of communication act is and ways of reaching that target via linguistic forms.

Generally, below given models consists of detailed requirements of language-related components as socio-linguistic and grammatical discourse knowledge have always been paid less attention and it was thought too tough to deal with non-linguistic, affective, cognitive, and volitional factors. Even though, all these mentioned factors have been discussed very well by Dell Hymes. He considered it as part of what he called ability. Harding (2014) in his overview of assessing of communicative language points out the need to act beyond those linguistic criteria which he believes to be restricted and tries to make sure that reflecting destitution of current communicative on test constructs are sufficient. As a consequence, a number of scholars in this field kept on carrying investigations to tackle this or that linguistic issues.

III. Participant profile

The case study speaks about observation of two first year students of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages. Both of them are eighteen years old and their nationality – Uzbek, which means they have been learning English as a foreign language. These students are really keen on acquiring a new language. They have learned English grammar properly before enrolling the institute and have satisfactory vocabulary stock. Unfortunately, they cannot communicate effectively and freely because of certain reasons. The reason why they have chosen to master their language skills is clear. One of them is going to become a guide interpreter while the other one intends to become an English teacher at school. Student A was brought up in a big family and has three siblings and grandparents. Student B was raised in rather small family and she lives with her parents and a younger brother. Participants have been learning English since school times, but both of them started to study it more seriously about two years ago. The student A had tried to communicate with foreign tourists in Registan square before starting institute courses, as she is desiring to become a good guide – interpreter in near future. She sometimes watches films in English. Meanwhile, Student B is fond of English songs and loves doing her home assignments listening to music. I have understood that these girls could not express themselves well. There were many hesitations, pauses in their speech. They couldn't help using Uzbek language to be comprehensible. Since, both students have achieved a great deal of success in communicative competence. Now, they are able to talk in general topics more freely. They apply various ways of learning, such as talking to tourists, chatting with friends and practicing language skills using textbooks provided for English courses. Results show out that, girls are relevant to my chosen topic as they lack communicating fluently in English language. During the small research it became visible that they have been more visual learners as they know a great many words and word-combinations when they read, but they cannot recall them well in their oral or written speech. Moreover, one can be assured that they possess good grammar and vocabulary skills if they are given test or exercises by the teacher. Unfortunately, when they are asked to write or tell something, incorrect grammatical structures and lack of academic vocabulary can be noticed easily and they had long pauses for searching proper words and tense, which teacher found controversial issue to be dealt with. It proves that, it was hard for them to acquire something only through listening

as they got used to reading a lot. Probably because of culture they did not prefer to expand their answers, but used short responses in most cases. While teaching them mentor tried to motivate them to speak do not paying much attention to the sentence structure but being able to convey the message.

IV. Research design

This case study includes the following steps:

- pre-interview and grammar, listening test
- watching videos (based on authentic materials)
- post interview

First of all, both participants were observed passively in some English classes in order to gain information about their knowledge, challenges and learning strategies. Pre-test (interview) with students were held at the beginning of this research and in that part each student were asked ten questions on different topics related to their free time activity and lifestyle in order to find out some data about their communicative competence. The interview was recorded for about 8 minutes for each student and teacher relistened it in order to analyse language competence prior to the second stage. Besides the interview the participants were asked several questions about their background and interests and were given grammar test, that proved their knowledge of grammar was quite amazing. Afterward, they watched short authentic videos without subtitles, which were found to be hard to follow by students. Then instructor asked them to write down anything they could catch. The answers were not much satisfactory. After that, he allowed them to watch video fragments with subtitles which aided them a lot to comprehend all dialogs then, they had a talk with each other on similar topics. It revealed they are more visual learners and did not have enough practice of authentic material. After a week, they were given a set of questions with various possible answers to read and discuss. Teacher explained that answers should not be too short but they have to provide some support or an example with each case. According to the given materials students practiced their listening and speaking skill for a certain period of time. Finally, last step post-interview was carried out so as to gain data about their impression and experience regarding the process and the method used for the improvement of their communicative competence. The interviews were recorded in English since they comprehend and be able to speak English.

V. Data Collection and Findings

It is undeniable that, in the classrooms we have to face a wide variety of language learning ways. One of them is visual learners, who mainly prefer acquiring knowledge through visual texts, words pictures, poster, etc. These kinds of students can easily get confused if they follow spoken instructions or speeches. Interestingly, they are not the only type of learners aided through visual aids; there are tactile or kinesthetic learners who like learning with palpable thing, cards and pictures too. In my opinion, when the students feel comfortable in the classroom with the given materials and the activities, they should do their best, possibly feeling self-confidence.

Although, the process of data collection is considered to be hard, it should be outlined that it was quite fun to observe chosen participants and help them to improve their communicative competence. Teacher started gaining information about students and their knowledge with curiosity because he wanted to know the solution of their problem of fluent communication in target language. For the purpose of collecting all needed data, initially he had to observe both girls in the classroom then, conducted pre interview, watching short authentic videos on several topics and doing some ranged grammar test. Finally, we had post interview to conclude all findings. By the end of the research it was clear that they became more confident to express their thoughts in the target language. So, all applied stages are as follows:

The mentor sad that on the first days he wanted observe both students passively during their English classes, where he found out that they do not respond to the teacher's questions at once but prepared their answers for certain period of time. Something interesting is that they tried hard to acquire the given handouts and kept learning vocabulary. Later he had a talk about their language problems. Then they recorded pre-interview, which dealt with asking questions on various themes mostly about themselves to check their listening as well as speaking skills. After, mentor had listened to records to find out information about deficiencies in their communication. Interestingly, he has

found out that Student A managed to convey messages better than Student B probably because she had some practice in real situations with tourists before. However, long pauses were noticed randomly in their speech and they paid too much attention to their grammatical structures as they tried to correct all of them in their speech, which interrupted successful communication. Student B, sometimes had to pause to search for proper words. They somehow found it hard to communicate spontaneously as they had got used to recite ready dialogs in school times. They occasionally, could not catch the questions and asked for either repetition or clarification. After the interview, they confessed in their native language that they felt a little bit shy and sometimes had to translate things from Uzbek into English in their minds. They were mostly taught through traditional methods unfortunately it affected their oral speech as they did not have much chance to speak on every day topics. Both students did the given grammar test much better than we expected, with some minor errors. It is vital to say that it took them less time to do grammar test. In the following step, they watched short video fragments which were difficult for them to understand at the beginning without any subtitles. Then instructor showed them subtitles. After reading the subtitles and listening at the same time they started to comprehend the meaning of dialogs much better. Then they practised these dialogs themselves and were able to have conversations on these topics in the classroom as well as outside. Participants had some problems with beginning phrases instead used direct responses, after practising for a while they became aware of their mistakes and tried hard to avoid it. Students were provided with pre interview questions and several possible responses for each. They looked through them exchanged ideas and teacher explained that even though if they are going to answer negatively the response should not be too short and they should provide some support or an example each time. Repetitive listening to audio tracks of videos, helped students in gaining confidence as they repeat and imitated real models using the target language. Therefore, students were expected to be more participative and feel more motivated. When it was high time to have post interview teacher was a little bit worried whether girl could cope with it or not. Fortunately, they were able to answer all questions well and we (me and teacher) can assure that they improved their:

- Level of attention;
- Participation;
- Better comprehension of native speakers (English);
- Immediate answers to the new input;

All in all, both participants were satisfied with the research and thanked for improving their communicative competence. Student A mentioned that she liked videos rather than reading question with various possible answers yet Student B found reading more productive. The results show that everyone's learning style differs as we have unique individualities, so various method should be applied in the process of teaching.

VI. Conclusion

This case study was mainly based on communicative competence theory as the goals were to be aware learners' challenges concerning communicative competence and find some ways of addressing them. The aim was to work on a topic relating to communication as most of students have such problems bachelor's degree. I consider our hypothesis was proven in this case study as noticed improvement in their communication. Through this case study all teacher beings learned that motivating students and various activities are useful to improve communication competence. As for me watching, listening is more fun than reciting dialogs, which will develop learners' comprehension of the language.

In order to make lessons more effective and enjoyable teachers should prepare lesson plans and interesting teaching materials by the help of various pedagogical methods for the new lesson beforehand. If they organize lessons interestingly and successfully, they can achieve their all goals. For every lesson they may use different materials related to their levels and prepare various activities or games appropriating to students' interests and levels. It is undeniable fact that all teachers should put a lot of aims before the lesson. For instance, they should say themselves in this lesson I should teach them these vocabularies, any grammatical theme or a funny game/activity and of course using the latest technologies. In this way, they can achieve their purposes. If they use different useful

interactive methods and innovative technologies most learners will improve their communicative competence better.

Hence, they should try to use more authentic material such as examples from real life during their English classes. Traditional lessons may be a quiet boring method for learners. In my opinion, human being is quite keen on games and songs and teacher could catch their attention by doing this. That is why using interesting videos and interactive games help teachers of English to improve students' communicative fluency faster than other methods. Namely role playing, dialogues, singing songs in a group, games, interview, oral presentation, reading aloud, questioning/answering are the most productive among them.

The most important thing in learning languages intensively is to persuade learners not to be afraid or shy to speak in target language. It will help them to develop their communicative skills and to enrich their vocabulary stock too. Frequently, when we are given any topic to speak, we think in our native language. Really, we may think in our native language but we should express quickly to produce a fluent speech in a foreign language.

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5 ЖИЛД, 6 СОН

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